

FLAMMABILITY, THERMAL AND MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF RESIN TRANSFER MOLDED POLYESTER / GLASS FIBER / MODIFIED CLAYS COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Glass reinforced / unsaturated polyester composites prepared by resin transfer molding (RTM) are widely applied in the automotive sector. Some fillers, e.g. calcium carbonate (CaCO₃), are commonly added to the resin to reduce costs and enhance some properties. These micro-particles are generally difficult to disperse on the resin, bringing drawbacks to the resulting composite. The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of new fillers, cation exchange and silane modified montmorillonite (MMT) nanoclays, on dispersion, and consequently, the mechanical, thermal properties and flammability of polyester/glass fiber composites, in comparison with composites prepared with calcium carbonate fillers. Montmorillonite clays Cloisite[®] Na⁺ (Mt-Na) and Cloisite[®] 30B (Mt-30B) were modified with methacryloxypropyltrimethoxysilane (MPS). The modified clays (Mt-Na(MPS) and Mt-30B(MPS)) were oven-dried for 10 h at 100 °C, grounded and sieved, then added to the polyester resin (at 3 wt.%). Homogenization was carried out by mechanical stirring followed by sonication. The composites were prepared using three glass fiber mats (~ 15 vol.%) by RTM technique, and the samples were named, for example, P-30B-GF, considering P (polyester), 30B (clay used) and GF (glass fiber). Filler dispersion was evaluated by DRX and TEM analysis, and P-30B-GF and P-30B(MPS)-GF samples showed greater basal spacing compared with P-Na-GF and P-Na(MPS)-GF samples, with an intercalated/exfoliated structure. Flexural strength and modulus increased with clay incorporation, particularly for silane-modified clays. A similar trend was found in the impact strength results. The coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) decreased with clay incorporation both below and above the glass transition temperature. These composites could be used in flame retardant formulations, acting as a physical barrier before combustion, and the P-30B(MPS)-GF sample showed reduction in the peak of heat release while P-30B-GF sample reduced the total of smoke release.

1 INTRODUCTION

Glass reinforced unsaturated polyester resins are a widely applied material in the automotive, building and naval industries and their performance optimization would enhance their range of applications even further. They may be used to produce multifunctional composites, for instance, if combined with nanomaterials [1,2]. The size of the reinforcement in composites and nanocomposites is very different. For example, the thickness of a layer of exfoliated silicate (1 nm) is approximately 10.000 times smaller than the diameter of a typical glass fiber. These two types of reinforcements can be combined into a three-phase composite. In the three-phase composite, the main

reinforcement is the fiber (which may be used in large quantities, such as 50 vol. %), which is responsible for the modulus and resistance of the material. The matrix, in this case, is a nanocomposite, containing particles at the nanometric scale. The nanoparticles take a portion of the space that would be occupied by the polymeric matrix. In composites, the properties that are dominated by the matrix, such as flexural or compression resistance may be improved by the addition of nanoclay [3].

Furthermore, in glass fiber-reinforced polymeric composites, the overall fire resistance and its performance, including the generation of smoke, is determined by the sum of the components (fiber and resin), as well as if there are predominantly positive (synergistic) or negative effects. The polyester resins contain a considerable amount (35 to 40%) of monomer, which is also endowed with the solvent function. The high concentration associated with the high intrinsic flammability of styrene increases the fire hazards of these resins. Consequently, this may limit some possible applications. Therefore, a number of flame retardants have been tested, however the weak adhesion between additive and polymer, as well as the large quantities that are used, may increase the cost and reduce the mechanical properties of the final composite [4,5]. Among the phyllosilicates having the flame retardant function (montmorillonite, hectorite, saponite), montmorillonite has received deeper attention. The improved performance observed is usually associated with reduced rate of heat release (HRR), experimental results being determined by cone calorimetry, and are most significant in concentrations up to 5 wt.% [6].

Conventional composites usually require a high content (> 10%) of the inorganic reinforcement, e.g. calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), to yield the final mechanical properties. These high concentrations will increase the density values of the product and may cause reduction in the final properties due to the incompatibility between the fiber reinforcement and the organic material. Furthermore, processing difficulties surge with increased reinforcement content. In contrast, the nanoparticles could improve thermal and mechanical properties on the basis of lower amount of incorporated clay (<5%) [7]. In order to facilitate compatibility with polyester resins, surface modification of the clay particles is desirable. The advantages of cation exchange modification are improved interlayer spacing and enhanced dispersion and interaction with the polymer matrix [8]. Another possibility is chemical modification of clay with silanes, which has the ability to interact with the polymeric matrix via covalent bond. Recently, silylation has proven to be effective in modifying the surface of clays [9-11]. In the resulting nanocomposites, the Si-OH group present in the silane will condense with the hydroxyl present on the surface of the clay and introduce special functional groups that will react with the polymer matrix [11].

Nowadays, the major studies related to polyester/clay nanocomposites are focused on evaluating mechanical properties such as tensile, flexural [1,12] and impact strength [13], and thermal properties such as enthalpy and thermal expansion coefficient [1]. Thus, several studies have been developed considering the incorporation of clay in polyester resins, mainly using organic modified clays. However, few studies are related to silane-modified clays compatible with a polyester resin. The explanation for that is related to the needs of industries to achieve multifunctional composites in order to improved mechanical and thermal properties and flammability.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

2.1 Materials

Montmorillonite clays Cloisite® Na and Cloisite® 30B were purchased from Southern Clay Company Products and calcium carbonate (CaCO_3) Mocalcium C325 from Itaplana Minérios LTDA. The unsaturated orthophthalic polyester resin UCEFLEX UC 5530-M was provided by the Elekeiroz S.A Company. Initiator methyl-ethyl-ketone peroxide in diisobutyl phthalate (Butanox LPT) was purchased from Akzo Nobel and accelerator dimethylaniline (DMA) were purchased from Rudnik. Methacryloxypropyltrimethoxysilane (MPS) were purchased from Aldrich's Company and the glass

fiber mats (300 g.cm⁻¹) were purchased from Owens Corning.

2.2 Clay Preparation

Silane (5 g) and ethanol PA (200 ml) were placed under magnetic stirring for 1 h. Meanwhile, the Cloisite® Na clay (10 g) and ethanol P.A (150 mL) / distilled water (150 mL) solution was dispersed by mechanical stirring for 40 min under 750 rpm. Both solutions were mixed and maintained under magnetic stirring during 24 h at 60 °C. The modified clay was oven-dried during 10 h at 100 °C, grounded and sieved (325 mesh). The same process was carried out with Cloisite 30B clay.

2.3 Composite Preparation

The clays were oven-dried for 60 min at 100 °C and then added to the polyester resin (3 wt.%). Homogenization was made by mechanical stirring at 750 rpm during 40 min. Sonication was performed during 3 cycles of 10 min under magnetic stirring followed by degassing for 20 min at 25 °C and - 0.4 bar in a vacuum oven. The composites were prepared by resin transfer molding (RTM). The parameters of the process were as follows: mold temperature between 20 and 25 °C, pressure between 0.25 and 0.50 bar and curing time of 1 h in situ and 24 h at 25 °C. The post-curing was performed for 6 h at 80 °C and then 2 h at 120 °C. The nanocomposites were named according to the filler used, as shown Figure 1. For example, the P-30B(MPS)-GF sample was prepared with polyester resin, clay 30B modified with MPS silane and glass fiber.

Figure 1. Denomination of the three-component composites

2.4 Characterization

Flexural strength measurements were carried out in a universal testing machine EMIC DL-3000 in accordance with ASTM D7264M-07. Samples of 128 x 13 x 4 mm³ were prepared and the test was conducted using a cell load of 200 kg at 1.8 mm.min⁻¹ rate of loading. Unnotched Izod impact test was performed using a CEAST impact machine, according to ASTM D256-10 standard. Samples (63.5 x 12.7 x 4 mm) were prepared, and the maximum energy of the hammer was 1 J. The average values of seven and ten samples for each condition were reported, respectively. The fracture after impact test was evaluated using a scanning electron microscope (SHIMADZU, SS-550 *Superscan*) operating from 10kW to 15 kW. The samples were oven-dried at 70°C with air circulation for 6 h and sputtered with a gold layer prior to SEM observations. Transmission electron microscopy was performed using a JEOL JEM 1200ExII microscope working with accelerating voltage of 80 kV. The samples were cut by

ultramicrotomy with a diamond knife, reaching a final thickness within 50-70 nm. Thermogravimetry (TGA - Shimadzu TGA-50) was performed at a heating rate of $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ in nitrogen and air atmosphere and in the temperature range from 25 to $800\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The thermomechanical analysis (TMA) was conducted (TMA-60 - SHIMADZU) in the range of 20 to $160\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a heating rate of $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ and 5 g loading, with samples dimensions of $8 \times 8 \times 4\text{ mm}$. The coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) was obtained from the slope of the curves of the L/L_0 versus T , where L_0 is the initial value of the thickness and L is the thickness value at a certain temperature T . Interrupted combustion tests were carried out by quenching the flame just after ignition, using nitrogen flow on the material surface and removing the specimen from the cone. The Limiting Oxygen Index (LOI) test was conducted according to the ASTM 2836 using a test specimen $70 \times 6.5 \times 4\text{ mm}$. The concentration of oxygen was increased if the specimen was extinguished before burning away for 3 min or 5 cm. The oxygen content was adjusted until the limiting concentration was determined. Horizontal burning testing was realized according to UL 94HB. The linear velocity of burning rate (V , in $\text{mm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) for each sample was calculated using $V = 60.L.t^{-1}$, where L is the damaged length (in mm) and t is time (in s). Combustion behavior was carried out on a Fire Testing Technology (FFT) cone calorimeter apparatus, the $50 \times 50 \times 4\text{ mm}$ samples in triplicate were irradiated at $35\text{ kW}/\text{m}^2$.

3 RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the X-Ray diffraction and TEM analysis of the two and three-component composites.

Figure 2. XRD and TEM analysis of two and three-components composites containing (a) Cloisite Na and (b) Cloisite 30B modified and non-modified samples

The MPS silylation improved the Cloisite Na clay dispersion for two and three-component composites (Figure 2a). Nevertheless, two-component composites 30B(MPS) tend to have an intercalated structure, but the diffractions in $2\theta = 2,4$ and $4,8$ disappear for the three-component composites (Figure 2b). Finally, the P-30B-GF and P-30B(MPS)-GF samples showed greater basal spacing compared with P-Na-GF and P-Na(MPS)-GF samples, with an intercalated/exfoliated structure.

Table 1 presents the mechanical results for the three-component composites. In general, flexural strength and modulus increased with clay incorporation, in special for those silane-modified clays P-Na(MPS)-GF and P-30B(MPS)-GF (~ 162 MPa and 165 MPa), in comparison with CaCO_3 composite (~ 143 MPa) and neat resin (~ 128 MPa). A similar trend was found for the impact strength results. For two component composites, the mechanisms responsible for increasing the flexural strength by clay addition are associated with dispersion and size of the agglomerates. Also, the composite modulus of the system increases with a growth of dispersion [7]. In this system, it is important to considerate the clay dispersion, but also as the interface glass-fiber and polyester resin are affected by clay addition.

<i>Sample</i>	<i>Flexural Strength (MPa)</i>	<i>Flexural Modulus (MPa)</i>	<i>Impact Strength (kJ/m²)</i>
PR-GF	128.5 ± 13.8	10070.9 ± 359.7	56.9 ± 4.0
P-Na-GF	155.2 ± 10.9	10524.2 ± 394.7	52.7 ± 3.5
P-Na(MPS)-GF	162.2 ± 5.9	11209.1 ± 297.5	60.8 ± 5.1
P-30B-GF	127.9 ± 1.9	8941.0 ± 67.5	47.6 ± 2.6
P-30B(MPS)-GF	165.9 ± 11.3	11131.3 ± 566.5	63.7 ± 6.2
P- CaCO_3 -GF	143.4 ± 7.8	10738.2 ± 385.6	52.1 ± 5.6

Table 1. Effect of clay silylation on the mechanical properties of the composites

Figure 3 shows the fracture after impact test for the studied samples. It was clear to see that the clays surrounded the glass fiber. For example, the P-Na-GF showed high concentration of clay agglomeration surrounding the glass fiber, and the size of the agglomeration reduced after silane-clay modification (P-Na(MPS)-GF). For P-30B-GF and P-30B(MPS)-GF samples, the agglomerates size decreases respect to the P-Na-GF samples. Peláez e Souza [14] studied composites of polypropylene, glass fiber and O-MMT Cloisite 20A and the presence of clays particles near the fiber surface damages the shear stress transfer at the fiber-polymer interface. At high levels of shear stress transfer at the fiber-polymer interface, the clay particles decouple, probably due to lower interfacial compatibilization with the polymer matrix, creating nanocracks that coalesce leading to greater size cracks and, therefore, contributing to premature fiber-polymer decoupling. The authors concluded that the reduction in mechanical performance is attributed to the physical presence of clay particles at the fiber-polymer interface contributing towards substantial reduction of shear stress transfer at the fiber-polymer interface. Therefore, the silane-modified clays could avoid the cracks formation at the interface, improving the stress transfer at glass-fiber and polyester interface, leading to improved mechanical properties. It was more difficult to find agglomerates at the P-30B(MPS)-GF sample and, in this case, good polyester-glass fiber interface was found.

Figure 3. SEM analysis of the three-component composites (magnification of 1000× and 5000×).

The clay silylation have an important role on the coefficient of thermal expansion, as shown in Table 2. In the glassy region (40 – 70 °C), the clay incorporation could decrease the free volume between chains. This is more evident for the samples containing silane-modified clay, probably due to the link between the clay and the resin by covalent bond, which could prevent the chain movements with increased temperature. In the rubbery region, according to Choudalakis & Gotsis [15], the clays do not contribute to the reduction of the CTE by increasing the movement of the polymeric chains, that way the clays do not act as reinforcement, failing to prevent the movement. In this situation, the higher crosslink density found in previous studies related to the resin could justify the reduction for the CTE values.

Sample	CTE ($\times 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$)	
	40-70 $^\circ\text{C}$	130-160 $^\circ\text{C}$
PR-GF	83.3	400.0
P-Na-GF	80.4	371.6
P-Na(MPS)-GF	55.6	368.9
P-30B-GF	71.3	366.1
P-30B(MPS)-GF	65.0	349.4
P-CaCO ₃	75.9	365.2

Table 2. Effect of clay silylation on the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of the samples studied

The thermogravimetric analysis for the samples in nitrogen (Figure 4a) and in oxidative air (Figure 4b) atmosphere showed different degradation behavior. Thermal degradation processes of samples in nitrogen consist of one main step related to the chain scission of polyester fragments corresponding to a DTG peak at ~ 409 $^\circ\text{C}$. Compared to the thermal oxidative degradation process in the air atmosphere, the main degradation step range was from 300 to 430 $^\circ\text{C}$, and this leads to the formation of a primary carbonaceous char, which degraded at high temperature around 540 $^\circ\text{C}$. The third decomposition step around 540 $^\circ\text{C}$ is due to the further char oxidation decomposition [16].

Figure 4. TGA analysis for the composites in (a) nitrogen and (b) air atmosphere

Table 3 shows the temperature at which the weight loss was approximately 10% and 60% (T10%) and (T60%), respectively, and the solid residual weight at 600 $^\circ\text{C}$. In nitrogen atmosphere, there are not significant thermal stability changes, as showed at T10% and T60%. However, the addition of clay could enhance the thermal stability of the material by assisting in the char formation during thermal decomposition [17]. It could be justified by the increased residual weight at 600 $^\circ\text{C}$, in comparison with the PR-GF samples. The P-CaCO₃ sample showed increased thermal stability at T60% and could also enhance the char formation, due to the increased residual weight.

The degradation behavior of the samples when evaluated in air displayed different results from those evaluated in nitrogen. All samples decomposed at lower temperatures when exposed to air atmosphere. The samples P-Na(MPS)-GF and P-Na-GF increased the thermal stability with respect to the PR-GF samples, and also the char residue at 600 °C. However, the samples prepared with organic modified clays (P-30B-GF and P-30B(MPS)-GF) decomposed before, and showed similar residual weight if compared with the composite PR-GF. This is in accordance with the behavior of the quaternary ammonium salts pyrolysis, which shows events of weight loss at 200 °C to 500 °C [18]. The reduction is also attributed to the lower crosslinking densities of these systems as demonstrated in previous studies. Also, it is important to mention that the P-Na(MPS)-GF, P-30B-GF and P-30B(MPS)-GF samples have inorganic content of 2,54 wt.%, 2,30 wt.% and 2,00 wt.%, respectively, if compared to P-Na-GF and P-CaCO₃-GF samples, which contains 3 wt.%. The P-CaCO₃ sample showed similar behavior to the PR-GF sample when evaluated in air atmosphere.

Sample	T10% (°C)		T60% (°C)		Residual weight (%) at 600 °C	
	N ₂	AIR	N ₂	AIR	N ₂	AIR
PR-GF	344	321	420	399	20	21
P-Na-GF	343	321	423	411	27	29
P-Na(MPS)-GF	344	328	418	409	33	26
P-30B-GF	344	316	421	402	29	22
P-30B(MPS)-GF	344	314	422	399	29	18
P-CaCO ₃	346	321	428	403	34	25

Table 3. Effect of clay silylation on the thermal analysis

Pre-ignition is the last phase before ignition and many thermoxidative reactions take place at this point. Surface barrier separating the sample from the flame is being formed during this phase [19]. In order to evaluate the pre-ignition phase, the interrupted combustion test at the time of ignition was performed (Figure 5) and all the samples containing fillers showed higher values related to time of ignition and higher surface char formation if compared with pristine composite.

Figure 5. Samples after the Interrupted Combustion Test at the Time to Ignition (TTI)

Clay particles also claimed to play a catalytic role on the promotion of char forming reactions. The catalytic effect of layered silicates on charring reactions derives mainly from the acid sites formed on

silicates due to the degradation of organic treatment, and from the OH present in the vertices and edges of the montmorillonite structures. The decomposition of alkylammonium salts proceeds, usually above 200 °C, either via the Hoffmann elimination reaction or via the S_N2 nucleophilic substitution reaction [20]. The silane also degrades usually above 200 °C. Furthermore, char formation during polymer degradation is generally a complex process involving several steps, which include conjugated double bond formation, cyclization, aromatization, fusion of aromatic rings, turbostratic char construction and graphitization. One mechanism proposed in the literature, at low temperatures, causes chain scission with subsequent volatilization of the polymer via free-radical chain reactions, generating mainly hydroperoxides and oxygenated species [20]. In this study, the char formation at the surface showed heterogeneous distribution for all samples, and consequently, the sample cross-section (Figure 6) showed irregular and more pronounced burned thickness visualized for the samples b and c. In fact in the Na-MMT case there are more available acid sites that can interact with the resin, while in the presence of organic modifier (30B) most of them are sterically hindered by the tallow chains. Optical microscopy (Figure 6c) for the Na(MPS)-GF showed a higher concentration of bubbles in the glass fiber regions. This behavior was found in all of the samples analyzed by optical microscopy. For this reason, before combustion, glass fiber showed an important role as physical barrier to the volatiles. Also, the clays dispersed in the resin act as a physical barrier before combustion, increasing the time to ignition if compared with the PR-GF sample.

Figure 6. Cross-section of the (a) resin, (b) P-Na-GF, (c) P-Na(MPS)-GF followed by the optical microscopy evidencing a glass fiber region and an scheme of the barrier clay effect, (d) P-30B-GF, (e) P-30B(MPS)-GF and (f) CaCO₃-GF.

Figure 7 shows the heat release rate (HRR) and the total of smoke release *versus* time for the composites studied. These curves are obtained from averaging the trial results for each experiment. They have a quite similar profile; however, comparing with the traditional CaCO₃ filler, the clays tend to decrease the heat release rate up to 300 s as well as the total of smoke release. Smoke, in particular, is a combination of complete, (CO₂, H₂O, and acid gases) incomplete (CO, soot, and partially oxidized fuel gases) combustion species, while the solid residue is mostly carbon and ash (oxidized metals). Reductions in smoke production and toxicity have been recorded to the barrier effect of silicates, which form tortuous paths for the diffusing molecules [20]. Further details of measured values are summarized in Table 4.

Although the peak of heat release rate ($pHRR$) did not change considerably (except for the P-30B(MPS)-GF), it is important to mention the reduction in the heat release rate (HRR) values found between 125 and 225 s. Probably, the reduction on the $pHRR$ could be related to the presence of a higher surface char formed in the clay composites before the time to ignition (Figure 5 and 6). After, reaching the peak, a sharp reduction of HRR values occurs and it could be related to the presence of the first layer of glass fiber. After this, a plateau region occurs between 125 and 225 s influenced by the synergic effect of the glass fiber and the clay, which acts as a physical barrier, reducing the rate of gas evolution from the specimen and, consequently, with a constant value of HRR . As confirmed by TGA, the clay samples could also enhance the char formation, due to the increased residual weight, as presented in Table 4. The char formation was more pronounced for the P-30B-GF and P-30B(MPS)-GF samples, confirmed by the presence of a higher amount of residues in these samples after the cone calorimeter test was performed, as illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 7. Average cone results for (a) Heat release rate (HRR) and (b) Total of smoke release (TSR)

As shown in Table 4, a reduction in the linear burning rate was more noticed for the samples with higher dispersion (P-30B-GF and P-30B(MPS)-GF). Regarding the LOI test, the more oxygen required (hence, the higher the LOI value), the better the material is considered to be flame retarded. Considering that air contains 21% oxygen, materials with a LOI value lower than 21 vol.% are categorized as flammable, while self-extinguishing materials are classified as the ones with LOI above 27 vol.%. This is because their combustion cannot be maintained at room temperature without the contribution of an external energy source [20]. For the studied composites, the limit of oxygen index (LOI) did not show significant changes with clay addition. However, the sample P-CaCO₃-GF diminished the LOI until the limit of 21 vol.%.

Sample	$t(ig)$ (s)	$pHRR$ (kW/m ²)	TSR (m ² /m ²)	Weight residual (%)	Linear burning rate (mm/min)	LOI (%)
PR-GF	85 ± 4	439 ± 9	4010 ± 22	25.7 ± 0.4	13.3 ± 0.83	21.7 ± 0.2
P-Na-GF	79 ± 2	412 ± 13	3886 ± 34	29.3 ± 0.3	10.8 ± 1.1	22.2 ± 0.2
P-Na(MPS)-GF	79 ± 3	409 ± 30	4004 ± 54	28.5 ± 0.6	10.8 ± 0.8	22.1 ± 0.2
P-30B-GF	87 ± 3	434 ± 22	3680 ± 62	30.6 ± 0.4	10.3 ± 0.4	21.6 ± 0.2
P-30B(MPS)-GF	82 ± 5	373 ± 30	3987 ± 13	29.7 ± 0.4	9.2 ± 0.5	21.5 ± 0.2
P-CaCO ₃ -GF	86 ± 2	446 ± 24	4205 ± 164	27.5 ± 1.0	11.8 ± 0.7	21.0 ± 0.2

Table 4. Linear burning rate, LOI and forced combusted (cono calorimeter) results for the studied samples

According to Kiliaris and Papaspyrides [20], the high propensity of nanocomposites to ignite, as

evidenced by cone calorimetry, has a negative impact on their performance in flammability tests, such as the LOI and UL 94. Furthermore, the barrier built by nanocomposites to reduce the pHRR under forced flaming conditions (cone calorimetry) is not sufficient for improving the extinction behavior when small flames are applied. In these tests, barrier properties play a minor role, while melt viscosity and dripping characteristics become the controlling factors for material's behavior against fire. For the LOI test, the specimen is burned in a candle-like configuration, more combustible material remains in the pyrolysis zone as a consequence of increased melt viscosity and wicking, regarding thermoplastic polymer. For thermosetting, the melt viscosity and dripping are not observed, indeed, it is important to consider the clay catalytic role on the promotion of char formation.

Figure 8. Sample residue of cone calorimeter test

4 CONCLUSIONS

The P-30B-GF and P-30B(MPS)-GF samples showed an improved basal spacing if compared with P-Na-GF and P-Na(MPS)-GF samples with an intercalated/exfoliated structure. The flexural resistance and modulus increased with the clay incorporation, in special, for those silane-modified clays and similar trends found for the impact strength results. The coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) values decreased in both regions, below and above the glass transition temperature, with clay incorporation. The improved mechanical and morphological performance related to the P30B(MPS)-GF sample could be justified by its better dispersion due to the cation exchange modification, consequently basal spacing improved and the compatible silane incorporated at the clay structure improve interactions with the polyester resin. All the samples decomposed at lower temperatures at air atmosphere and their degradation behaviors display different results from those exposed to nitrogen. These composites acted as a physical barrier before combustion, and the P-30B(MPS)-GF sample showed reduction in the peak of heat release while P-30B-GF sample reduced the total of smoke release. It was clear that the addition of 3 wt.% of clay in polyester and glass fiber systems should be combined with conventional flame retardants, in order to develop synergistic systems with high efficiency and acceptable environmental impact.

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